

Generic Method for Designing Self-Standing and Dual Porous 3D Bioscaffolds from Cellulosic Nanomaterials for Tissue Engineering Applications

Tamilselvan Mohan,* Andreja Dobaj Štiglic, Marco Beaumont, Johannes Konnerth, Fazilet Gürer, Damjan Makuc, Uroš Maver, Lidija Gradišnik, Janez Plavec, Rupert Kargl, and Karin Stana Kleinschek*

Cite This: *ACS Appl. Bio Mater.* 2020, 3, 1197–1209

Read Online

ACCESS |

Metrics & More

Article Recommendations

Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Three-dimensional scaffolds (3D) with controlled shape, dual porosity and long-term mechanical and dimensional stability in biofluids are of interest as biotemplates in tissue engineering. Herein, self-standing and lightweight cellulose-based biogenic scaffolds with a spatially structured morphology, macropores and interconnected micropores were fabricated using a combination of direct ink writing 3D printing and freeze-drying techniques. This was achieved by developing a water-based and low-cost bicomponent ink based on commercially available nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC) and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC). Physical cross-linking through dehydrothermal treatment significantly increased the surface hardness, indentation modulus, compression strength, as well as the dimensional stability of the scaffolds in biofluids, in comparison to untreated materials. However, no differences in the spectra of solid state nuclear magnetic resonance or infrared were observed for dehydrothermal treated samples, suggesting that the increase of mechanical properties and dimensional stability is based on the physical cross-linking of functional groups both at the interface between NFC and CMC. The supramolecular structure of the polymers was well-preserved as disclosed by X-ray diffraction measurements. The cross-linked scaffolds showed high proliferation, viability, and attachment of human bone tissue derived osteoblast cells (hFOB). The simple and straightforward avenue proposed here for the design of cellulose-based fibrous inks and dual porous scaffolds from the commercially available materials and without the need of any additional cross-linkers should pave the way for the development of implantable, degradable scaffolds and cell-laden biomaterials for bone tissue regeneration and 3D bioprinting applications.

KEYWORDS: 3D printing, freeze-drying, scaffolds, dual porosity, nanofibrillated cellulose, carboxymethyl cellulose, solid-state NMR, cell testing

1. INTRODUCTION

Inspired by biomimetics, engineering of three-dimensional (3D) scaffolds with ordered architectures has received great attention in various sectors of biomedical engineering, including cellular, genetic, and tissue engineering (TE).¹ Multiscale functional and porous scaffolds have been applied to mimic the extracellular matrix (ECM) and to support the growth and regeneration of various cells and human tissues.^{1,2} The techniques available for the fabrication of such scaffolds are a manifold and range from electrospinning to injection molding.³ Using these techniques, however, control over morphology, porosity, and interconnectivity is still a demanding task. 3D printing, on the contrary, is capable of creating customized scaffolds with high structural complexity and design flexibility for soft (e.g., cartilage) and hard (e.g., bone) TE applications.^{1,4,5} Direct ink writing (DIW), 3D printing in particular, has received great interest owing to its

usefulness for the fabrication of scaffolds from hydrogels based on polysaccharides, DNA, peptides, and proteins.^{1,6} With this technique, hydrogels designed as inks are extruded through a nozzle to fabricate complex scaffolds with fine features. The mentioned (bio)-applications often require scaffolds with spatial resolution and interconnected macro- and micropores. The macropores (200–400 μm) support tissue ingrowth, nutrient supply, and waste removal, while micropores (40–100 μm) can facilitate cell adhesion and influence mechanical properties.^{7,8} Integration of these two types of pores in one system is challenging and cannot be realized by using DIW

Received: November 29, 2019

Accepted: January 16, 2020

Published: January 16, 2020

alone. This can be overcome by the introduction of spatially resolved macropores by 3D printing and interconnected micropores by freeze-drying as we proposed in this study, compared to other reported works.^{9,10} While such hierarchically structured scaffolds can be composed of various synthetic biomaterials, polysaccharides have been increasingly utilized in TE, due to their cytocompatibility, natural availability, and dispersibility or solubility in aqueous systems.¹¹ Plant derived polysaccharides such as nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC) have been used to produce strong and lightweight scaffolds, because of their high surface area, flexibility, size (fibril width, 5–20 nm), and good mechanical properties.^{12,13} In addition, they are known to readily support crucial cellular processes during culturing of different cell types (e.g., human pluripotent stem cells, chondrocyte, etc.)^{1,14} and to biomimic the mechanical functions of physiological collagen, the main components of ECM.¹⁵

Reports on the fabrication of dimensionally stable scaffolds from NFC ink alone are scarce; the fibrils are often combined with naturally occurring biomaterials such as alginates, hyaluronic acid (HA), or gelatin to improve the ink viscosity and stabilize the printed structures.¹ As a substitute for these biomaterials, water-soluble carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) is a promising alternative with structural similarities to NFC. CMC shows an intrinsic affinity to NFC via interfacial adhesion¹⁶ and thereby can add flexibility, strength, and shape fidelity to the printed scaffolds similar to what was observed for alginate.⁹ Besides its well-known application in skin TE,^{1,17–19} CMC could also simulate the properties of glycosaminoglycans found in cartilage. Multistep chemical cross-linking methods are frequently employed to increase mechanical strength and dimensional stability of the printed scaffolds.²⁰ Chemical cross-linking is however often non-aqueous or requires a prior derivatization of the materials with reactive functional groups. This can be associated with cytotoxicity and can require rinsing procedures for cross-linker removal. Mechanical and dimensional stability of hydrogels are often not sufficiently increased despite cross-linking. In such cases, freeze-drying of polymer NFC dispersions are useful as it can preserve shapes and structural fidelity. In addition, it has the potential to create interconnected micropores due to the formation of solvent crystals during freezing.²¹ Another alternative to chemical cross-linking is dehydrothermal treatment (DHT) in the dry state which avoids solvents and is used to enhance the mechanical properties of collagen biomaterials.^{22,23} To our knowledge, a combination of DIW, freeze-drying, and DHT was not published for polysaccharide scaffolds. While studies demonstrated the fabrication of wet NFC scaffolds via DIW, solid, or wet self-standing and spatially structured scaffolds with dual porosity from an aqueous NFC/CMC ink have not been reported until now. Such cross-linker free and dimensionally stable wet scaffolds made from natural polysaccharides are biocompatible and should be suitable therefore for long-term *in vitro* cell culturing experiments. Due to the available surface functional groups (e.g., carboxyl and hydroxyl), the solid NFC/CMC scaffold can be further heterogeneously functionalized with different cell binding molecules like peptides or ECM proteins through a simple chemical pathway (e.g., carbodiimide or click-chemistry).

The aim of the present study was therefore to develop self-standing, dual-porous, and mechanically and dimensionally stable wet or dry scaffolds from cellulose-based biocompatible nanomaterials. To achieve this, inks composed of NFC/CMC

were prepared and their rheological properties investigated in detail. Printable inks were then shaped into wet scaffold by DIW. Dry and self-standing scaffolds with interconnected micropores were then obtained by freeze-drying and subsequent DHT of the prints. The morphological, chemical, structural, thermal, and mechanical properties of the scaffolds were then analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), infrared spectroscopy, solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), X-ray diffraction, thermogravimetric analysis, nanoindentation, and compression strength analysis. The suitability of these biogenic scaffolds in TE were demonstrated by biocompatibility and proliferation tests using human bone tissue derived osteoblast cells (hFOB) as a model system.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Materials. Carboxymethyl cellulose sodium salt (CMC, DS_{COOH}: 0.9; M_w: 700 kDa) and phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (BioPerformance certified, pH 7.4) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany. Nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC, 3 wt %) was purchased from the University of Maine, Process Development Center. Ultrapure water (Milli-Q system, Millipore) was used for the preparation of all samples. Advanced Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (ADMEM) and Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) were purchased from ThermoFisher, Germany.

2.2. Preparation of Composite Inks for DIW. The following procedure was used for the preparation of cellulose-based composite inks for DIW. CMC (see Table 1) was added Milli-Q-water and

Table 1. Preparation of Inks Based on Nanofibrillated Cellulose (NFC) and Carboxymethyl Cellulose (CMC) and Their Final Compositions^a

inks	CMC (g)	water (g)	NFC ^a (g)	final NFC (wt %)	final CMC (wt %)
NFC		50	50	1.5	0
CMC	6	94		0	6
NC1	1.5	48.5	50	1.5	1.5
NC2	3	47	50	1.5	3
NC3	6	44	50	1.5	6

^a3 wt % suspensions in water.

stirred with a laboratory mechanical stirrer (IKA EUROSTAR 20) at 1000–3000 rpm for 30 min. To this, 50 g of NFC (3 wt %) was added, stirred with a mechanical stirrer at 1500 rpm until no NFC fibers were seen (~30 min). The samples (inks) were covered with an aluminum foil and stored in the refrigerator at 2–8 °C until further use. All inks were equilibrated to room temperature before the rheological and 3D printing experiments. The inks were labeled as described in Table 1.

2.3. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). AFM was used for the topographical analysis of air-dried NFC and NC3 ink samples. Volumes of 100 μL of 0.01 wt % of both inks (dispersed in water) were dropped onto cleaned Silicon-wafers (1.5 × 1.5 cm², Topsil, Germany, with 100 surface orientation) and dried at ambient temperature for 8 h. The air-dried samples were analyzed using the Keysight 7500 AFM (Keysight Technologies). Topography images were acquired using the acoustic ac AFM mode. Silicon AFM tips (Nanosensors, Switzerland) with a nominal spring constant 12–110 N/m and a nominal resonance frequency of 210–490 kHz were used for imaging purposes for all samples. Images were recorded, with a resolution of at least 524 × 524 pixels. All images were processed using the freeware Gwyddion.²⁴

2.4. Rheology. The rheological properties of all inks were measured with a Bohlin Instruments (Gloucester, England) CVO 50 rheometer. All measurements were performed at 25 °C using a cone-plate measuring system (4°/40 mm) with a gap size of 200 μm. The

shear viscosity was measured at shear rates from 0.1 s⁻¹ to 100 s⁻¹. Oscillation amplitude sweeps were performed with a shear stress from 1 to 1000 Pa at a frequency of 1 Hz and frequency sweeps were measured with a constant shear stress of 20 Pa in a frequency range of 10⁻²–10² Hz.

2.5. 3D Printing, Freeze-Drying, and Deydrothermal Treatment (DHT). 3D printing of the inks (Table 1) was performed using a BioScaffolder 3.1 (GeSiM, Germany). A 10 mL polyethylene-based plastic syringe (Nordson, U.K. Limited) with an inner nozzle diameter of 250 μm was used to dispense the inks on a polystyrene Petri dish (diameter, 5 cm). The syringe was tightly packed with ink and stored at 8 °C until further use. Circular scaffolds (radius, 5 mm; height, 6 mm; number of corners at the edge, 100) were built in a layer-by-layer fashion. These dimensions were created by using GeSiM Robotics BS3.1/3.2 software. Scaffolds were printed by adjusting the dispensing pressure from pressure 220 kPa–260 kPa (Method I) and the distance between strands from 500 μm–900 μm (Method II) at a pressure of 260 kPa. The strand height and width were set to 0.2 mm. The printing patterns of each subsequent layer were rotated by 90° and the printing speed was 15 mm/s. For wet compression tests, scaffolds with a height of 10 mm were printed using the same parameters as mentioned above.

The printed samples (NC3) were frozen at -25 °C for 48 h in a freezer followed by freeze-drying for 48 h at 10⁻³ mbar and -25 °C. The freeze-dried sample is denoted as NC3-F. After freeze-drying, the dry scaffolds were physically cross-linked by DHT.^{22,23} Scaffolds were placed in a glass container, covered completely with aluminum foil, and kept in a vacuum oven (VacuCell 22; MMM, Munich, Germany) at 100 mbar at different temperatures (60, 90, and 120 °C) for 6, 12, 18, and 24 h, respectively. The cross-linked samples are named as “NC3-F-DHT/*x*/*y*” where *x* is the temperature in °C and *y* is the cross-linking time at temperature *x* in hours.

2.6. Potentiometric Charge Titration. The potentiometric charge titration of the sample solutions/dispersions was carried out with a two-buret automatic titrator T70 (Mettler Toledo) under an inert atmosphere (nitrogen gas bubbling). The CMC, NFC, NC3-F, and NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h samples (1.5 mg mL⁻¹) were titrated in forward (acidic to alkaline) and backward (alkaline to acidic) manners between 2 < pH < 11. All measurements were repeated thrice. A detailed description of the potentiometric charge titration method can be found elsewhere.²⁵ The amounts of charged groups present in the products are expressed in mmol g⁻¹ sample.

2.7. Solid-State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR). Solid-state NMR spectra were acquired on an Agilent Technologies NMR system 600 MHz NMR spectrometer equipped with 3.2 mm NB dual resonance HX MAS probe. Larmor frequency of the carbon nuclei was 150.75 MHz. ¹³C NMR chemical shifts are reported relative to TMS (δ 0.0 ppm). Samples were spun at 16 000 Hz.

2.8. Attenuated Total Reflectance-Infrared (ATR-FTIR) Spectroscopy. The ATR-FTIR spectra of scaffolds were measured using a PerkinElmer FTIR system Spectrum GX series-73565 at a wavenumber range of 4000–650 cm⁻¹. A total of 32 scans were performed for all measurements with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.9. Powder X-ray Diffraction (XRD). The X-ray diffraction of the polymers, freeze-dried and heated 3D printed scaffolds, was investigated using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Bruker D8 Advance equipped with Cu Kα radiation). The scaffolds were cut into small pieces and deposited on the sample holder, and the XRD patterns were recorded at room temperature between a scattering angle (2θ): 10° to 50° and steps of 0.02° and scan rate of 0.02° 2θ s⁻¹.

2.10. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). TGA was performed on a PerkinElmer (Waltham, MA) TGA 4000 thermal analysis instrument in a nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL min⁻¹) from 40 to 900 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ using an Al₂O₃ crucible without a lid. For data evaluation, the Pyris software, version 10.02.0468, was used.

2.11. Optical and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy Analysis. The morphology and macropore size of wet printed structures were observed under an optical microscope (EVOS, FL Cell Imaging System, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Germany)

using 4× magnification. The image analysis freeware ImageJ 1.47 (NIH)²⁶ was used to evaluate the macropore size (strand distance) of the scaffold and the printed strand diameter from the images. The result is reported as the arithmetic mean and standard deviation from at least 10 measurements.

The morphology of dry scaffolds was analyzed by FESEM. A Carl Zeiss FE-SEM SUPRA 35 VP electron microscope was used. The images were recorded with an acceleration voltage of 1 kV. The samples were mounted on sample holders, and no sputtering on the sample surfaces was performed. The micropores seen on the strand surface and interior/cross-section of the sample were calculated by analyzing the SEM images (given in Figure 4, NC3-F (A and C), NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h (E and G) using the ImageJ 1.47 software, and at least 50 pores were chosen for each analysis.

2.12. Analysis of Swelling Capacity and Weight Loss. The swelling kinetics of the scaffolds in ADMEM + 5 wt % FBS (designated as biofluid, BF) were investigated by a gravimetric method.²⁷ The NC3-F scaffold that was heated at different temperatures (60–120 °C) for 24 h, and the NC3-F scaffold that was heated for 120 °C at different time intervals (6–24 h) was used for the swelling test. These dried and heated scaffolds were weighed (initial weight, *W*₀), immersed in 30 mL of BF (pH 7.4) at 37 °C. At predetermined time intervals (*W*_{*t*}), the scaffolds were removed from the liquid, carefully wiped dry by a filter paper only on the surface, and weighed again. The swelling capacity at time *t* was calculated using eq 1.

$$\text{Swelling capacity (\%)} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

For determining the weight loss upon contact with the liquid, the scaffolds (initial weight, *W*₀) were placed in a beaker with 30 mL of BF (pH 7.4) at 37 °C and stirred at 250 rpm. At predetermined time intervals, the scaffolds were removed from the BF, washed with Milli-Q-water three times, and freeze-dried. The remaining weight (RW) of the scaffolds was calculated as

$$\text{Remaining weight (\%)} = \frac{W_t}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where *W*_{*t*} is the dry weight of the scaffold at the predetermined time. Results are reported as arithmetic mean values and the standard deviation of triplicates.

2.13. Mechanical Strength Analysis. To measure the surface mechanical properties, nanoindentation was performed on the scaffold “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” in air and biofluid using an Anton Paar Austria, Bioindenter, (UNHT³ Bio) with a ruby spherical indenter of 500 μm radius. The loading rate was set from 40 μN min⁻¹ to a maximum of 20 μN min⁻¹ with 30 s hold at the maximum load followed by unloading at 40 μN min⁻¹. The maximum indentation depth was fixed to 100 μm. For the experiments in biofluid, the scaffolds were completely immersed in the medium to avoid drying and hence changes of their mechanical properties. Before the nanoindentation was started, each region of the scaffold was visualized, and the target area of indentation was chosen under the microscope. The indentation modulus was calculated using a Hertzian fit to the loading data. We performed at least 10 measurements of each region on every sample with a sideward displacement of 500 μm. The measurements were performed using three independent scaffolds at ambient temperature.

Compression testing was performed for “NC3-F-DHT/*x*/*y*” scaffolds. Before the measurements, the scaffolds were completely immersed in BF for 2 h at ambient temperature. After equilibration in the medium, the scaffold had a diameter of 10 mm and a thickness of 6 mm on average, measured with a digital calliper. A universal material testing machine (Z020, Zwick Roell, Germany) equipped with a 500 N load cell was used for the unconfined compression test. The strain rate was set to 2.4 mm min⁻¹ and samples were compressed to 40% of the initial height. After compression, the elastic relaxation to 5% of the maximum stress (at 40%) at a relaxation rate of 2.4 mm min⁻¹ was determined. The elastic modulus was calculated from the slope in the

Figure 1. AFM images of air-dried NFC (A,B) and NC3 inks (C,D).

initial stage of the stress–strain curve and the compressive stiffness from the tangent modulus at 30% strain for all samples ($n = 3$ per group) according to the literature.⁹

2.14. Biocompatibility Testing with Osteoblast Cells. The biocompatibility of the inks and scaffolds on cell viability was evaluated via the reduction reaction of the tetrazolium salt MTT (3(4,5 dimethylthiazolyl-2)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide), purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany.^{28,29} Both inks and scaffolds were exposed to the UV light for 30 min for sterilization. The samples were soaked in 4 mL of ADMEM supplemented with 5 wt % FBS and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 5 wt % CO₂. The human bone tissue derived osteoblast cells (hFOB, ATCC, U.K.) (10 000 cells/well) were seeded into a 96-well microliter plate with a final volume of 100 μ L of ADMEM–5 wt % FBS. The material samples (supernatants of the starting samples) were added to the cells after 24 h of incubation at 37 °C in 5 wt % CO₂ in four parallels and in several dilutions (undiluted, 1:2, 1:4, 1:8, 1:16, and 1:32). As control, ADMEM–5 wt % FBS was added to the cells. After 24 h of treatment, cell viability was determined using the MTT test.^{18,30} For this purpose, 10 wt % reagent was added to the medium and discarded after 3 h. Then, DMSO was added, and after 5 min, the absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nm using the Varioskan multiplate reader (ThermoFisher, Germany).

To get further insight into the cell viability after their exposure to the scaffolds, a so-called “cell attachment or direct exposure test” was performed. For this purpose, a Live/Dead assay (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany; it includes Calcein-AM, which dyes only living cells (green color), and propidium iodide (PI), which dyes only dead cells (the dye cannot penetrate intact cell membranes)³¹) and served at the same time as an additional proof (apart from the above-described quantitative MTT assay) of the prepared materials’ biocompatibility toward the target cells tested (human bone-derived osteoblasts, hFOB 1.19 (ATCC CRL-11372), ATCC, U.K.). Prior to performing the test, all samples were sterilized under UV light for 30 min. The next step was sample incubation in P12 microtiter plates filled with a cell suspension containing 60 000 cells and the cell culturing media (Advanced Dulbecco’s modified Eagle’s medium, ADMEM, Gibco), supplemented by 5 wt % FBS. The samples were incubated together

with the cells, which were seeded onto the samples, for 72 h at 37 °C and in an atmosphere containing 5 wt % CO₂. After incubation, the tested samples were rinsed with PBS (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), followed by incubation in 4 mM calcein-AM and 2 mM PI solutions, respectively. Both solutions were prepared in PBS. The sample incubation with the Live/Dead kit was performed for 30 min at 37 °C. The final step in the process, was another washing of the samples with PBS. After the mentioned procedure, the samples were cut into several parts (see Figure S10). The top surface and cross-section of the cut samples were observed under a fluorescent microscope (EVOS FL Cell Imaging System, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Germany).

Statistical Analysis. All numerical values are given as the arithmetic mean and standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Statistics 25 (IBM Corp. Armonk, NY). By using the Shapiro-Wilk test, it was determined that all experimental data were normally distributed, allowing the use of one-way ANOVA. P -values <0.05 were considered to be statistically significant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Preparation and Characterization of Base Materials. Prior to analysis of 3D printed samples, the morphology of NFC and NC3 inks that were drop-casted and air-dried on silicon wafer was analyzed by AFM (Figure 1). The AFM height (Figure 1A) and phase (Figure 1B) images of NFC shows fibrils with a diameter of approximately 20 nm and thick fibrillar bundles with one ranging from 50 to 140 nm. The ink NC3 (Figure 1C,D) has a clearly different surface morphology, and the NFC fibrils (white arrows in Figure 1C) are in this case homogeneously embedded into a matrix of CMC.

Following the AFM analysis of the inks, we investigated the printability of pure NFC and CMC. We thoroughly studied extrusion of the inks at different pressures ranging from 10 to 300 kPa, but in all experiments, the flow through the printing nozzle was neither constant nor uniform, making pure NFC or

Figure 2. Rheological study of the inks: Viscosity curves (A) and frequency-dependency of the storage shear moduli (B) of the inks in comparison to pure nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC) and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC).

Figure 3. (A,B) Light microscopy images of the macropores of wet scaffolds, (C,D) pore-size of as-printed NC3 ink, NC3-F, and “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” scaffolds printed at different strand distances and pressures, and (E, F, and G) images of as-printed NC3 ink, NC3-F, and “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” scaffolds.

CMC unsuitable for printing (Figure S1). Based on these materials, we prepared three different inks with constant solid content of NFC (1.5 wt %), i.e., NC1–3 (Table 1) for DIW. The rheological properties of these composite inks are compared to pure NFC (1.5 wt %) and CMC (6 wt %) in Figure 2. In general, all investigated fluids featured shear thinning behavior (Figure 2A) and increasing the NFC/CMC ratio increased the viscosity. Up to an NFC/CMC mass ratio of 2 (NC1 and NC2), the inks had lower viscosity than the pure NFC or CMC. The highest viscosity featured the sample NC3, containing 1.5 wt % of NFC and 6 wt % CMC (mass ratio of 4). This ink had even higher viscosity and shear-thinning behavior than pure CMC and NFC. This suggests that intrinsic interactions between NFC and CMC favor the rheological flow behavior and explains the excellent printing capability of NC3 (Figure S2).

The frequency sweeps of NC1–3 and pure components in Figure S3 shows that all investigated suspensions (inks and starting materials) behave as a rheological gel or soft solid (storage modulus G' is higher than loss modulus G''). In all cases, the values of the moduli increased gradually with increasing frequency for both NFC and CMC inks. This effect is most pronounced in case of pure CMC, which represents from all these samples the “weakest” gel. In Figure 2B, the frequency dependency of the shear moduli of NC3 is directly compared to NFC and CMC and further confirms the conclusions from the viscosity curves. NC3 features the highest storage modulus of these samples. This suggests that the interaction between NFC and CMC is strong and the gel state ($G' > G''$) is not disturbed even at higher frequency range. This trend is also shown in the frequency dependency of the loss tangent (Figure S4). NC3 features the lowest loss

Scheme 1. Development of Self-Standing and Lightweight 3D Bioscaffolds with Macroporous and Interconnect Microporous Morphology from Bicomponent Ink Containing NFC and CMC via the Combination Of DIW 3D Printing, Freeze-Drying and DHT Techniques

NC3-F

NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h

Figure 4. SEM images of the freeze-dried scaffolds before (upper row) and after (lower row) DHT: (A,E) top surface, (B,F) cross-section with 100 \times fold, (C,G) 250 \times fold, and (D,H) 5.00k \times magnification.

tangents, which demonstrates that this ink shows the most pronounced elastic behavior of all investigated, making it suitable to form self-standing and stable DIW structures after extrusion, which is resistant to plastic deformation.

3.2. Pore Size and Morphology of the Wet and Dry Scaffolds. For creating scaffolds with variable pore sizes and dimensional stability, we varied the following printing settings: the dispensing pressure (Method I) and the distance between the printed strands (Method II). In both methods, we used NC3 as ink. Following Method I, the size of the printed macropores in the wet scaffolds was successfully controlled from 450 to 200 μm by simply tuning the pressure from 200 to 260 kPa with a fixed strand distance of 900 μm (Figure 3A,B). Variation of the strand distance (Method II) with a constant pressure of 260 kPa (Figure 3C) was chosen, and the strand distance was varied from 500 to 900 μm , and this allows further control of the macropore size. At a strand distance 500

μm , the lowest pore size of $200 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$ was obtained. In general, the pore size was tunable between 200 and 500 μm , which is an adequate size to allow growth and proliferation of bone cells inside the scaffold.^{32,33} As shown in Figure 3C,D, the freeze-dried (NC3-F) scaffold showed an increased macropore size for scaffolds with variable pore sizes and dimensional stability, and we varied the following printing settings: the dispensing pressure (Method I) and the distance between the printed strands (Method II). In both methods, we used NC3 as the ink. This effect is more pronounced for Method II. It is assumed that in Method II, the larger strand distance reduces the freezing speed and thereby the size of the nucleated ice crystal is increased. These ice crystals have a templating effect,³⁴ explaining the larger pore size after this treatment. Cross-linking of the freeze-dried scaffolds (NC3-F) through DHT treatment did not cause macroscopic shrinkage of the scaffold and its shape was retained (Figure 3E–G).

Figure 5. ATR-FTIR spectra (A), XRD (B), and TGA curve (C,D) of NFC, CMC, and NC3-F scaffolds before and after dehydrothermal treatment.

Thereby we produced lightweight and self-standing scaffolds in dry state, allowing an easy handling for cell culturing as well as further physicochemical analysis. We also showed that it was possible to produce lightweight scaffolds in different forms (see Figure S5, Scheme 1), suitable for various applications, using the ink NC3. Upon subjection to DHT at 120 °C the macropore size of the scaffolds was reduced (Figure 3C,D). However, no color change (this would be a sign of cellulose degradation) and only a slight mass change of about 4 wt % were observed (Figure 3G). The weight loss is related to the removal of adsorbed water or dehydration reactions. As suggested by other authors^{35,36} and in our previous work,³⁷ the reduction of the macropore size can be partially attributed to stronger H-bond formation between the different NFC and CMC chains and pore shrinkage caused by water removal.

For all further analysis, scaffolds such as NC3-F and “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” produced by Method II with a pore size of 220 μm (Figure 3B, right) at a pressure of 260 kPa were chosen. A clear difference in the surface morphology, geometrical accuracy, and pore size between NC3 and “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” was observed (Figure 4A,E). After DHT, the pore size decreased from 220 ± 14 μm to 200 ± 8 μm. Although the inner diameter of the printing nozzle was 250 μm, the printed single strand had an average width of 265 ± 5 μm which decreased to 240 ± 8 μm after DHT. The increase in strand width is due to the spreading of ink after the deposition. The surface roughness of the strand was decreased after DHT. While macropores (>200 μm) were controlled by DIW, the micropores (<100 μm) were obtained through ice templating (via freeze-drying). As shown in Figure 4, these micropores are distributed over the entire surface and in the cross-section of each strand of freeze-dried scaffolds. The observed size of pores on the strand surface of NC3-F sample is in the range of 20–80 μm, while at the interior/cross section of the sample they are mostly between 50 and 80 μm. After

DHT, a reduction in the amount and size of pores on the strand surface and the cross-section was clearly observed (Figure 4B,F and in magnification Figure 4C,G). On the strand surface of this sample, the sizes of pores are between 20 and 30 μm, which are rather 2-fold smaller than the ones seen on the strand surfaces of NC3-F. At the interior/cross-section, the sizes of pores in the DHT scaffold are between 20 and 90 μm. Further magnification (Figure 4D,H) shows the incorporation of NFC in a matrix of CMC. Overall, using the combined processing techniques of DIW and freeze-drying, we fabricated cellulose-based scaffolds with interconnected porosity, similar to scaffolds obtained from collagen-based biomaterials.³⁸ Scaffolds possessing such multiscale porous structure are important not only for cell attachment, cell–cell interaction, cell migration but also allow the control of (a) the mechanical properties, (b) the fluid uptake of the scaffold, and (c) the transfer of nutrients and metabolic waste products of cells inside the scaffold.³⁹ For example, Tienen et al.⁴⁰ and Matisko et al.⁴¹ reported that the macropores (150–355 μm) which are interconnected with micropores (<50 μm) were found to significantly improve fibrocartilage tissue regeneration and stimulate expression of chondrogenic genes.

3.3. Charges, Chemical Composition, Structure, and Thermal Properties. According to the pH-dependent charge titration (see Figure S7), the calculated amounts of carboxylic groups were 0.35 ± 0.05 mmol g⁻¹ for NFC and 3.51 ± 0.17 mmol g⁻¹ for CMC. NC3-F had a value of 3.72 ± 0.2 mmol g⁻¹, which was reduced to 50% (1.8 ± 0.12 mmol g⁻¹) by DHT. This suggests that the functional groups of NFC and CMC are strongly and physically cross-linked by DHT, which restricted the accessibility of carboxylic groups on both NFC and CMC, and thus reduced charges. Figure 5 shows the ATR-FTIR spectra of the polymers and NFC/CMC scaffolds before and after DHT. Pure NFC shows the bands at 3337 cm⁻¹, 2910 cm⁻¹, between 1300 and 1500 cm⁻¹, and at around 1060

Figure 6. Swelling capacity scaffolds: (A) NC3-F and NC3-F-DHT/60–120 °C/24 h and (B) NC3-F and NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/6–24 h. (C) Images of “NC3-F and NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” scaffold taken after the swelling test in biofluid at different time intervals (C).

cm^{-1} attributed to the O–H, C–H, C–H, and C–O stretching and the C–O–C vibration of the pyranose ring, respectively. The IR band at 1653 cm^{-1} corresponds to the O–H vibration of adsorbed water. For CMC, the characteristic peaks for O–H, C–H, and carboxyl stretching vibrations were detected at $3298, 2910, 1587, 1415,$ and 1324 cm^{-1} . In the case of NC3-F, the observed bands at $2896, 1590, 1017,$ and 1046 cm^{-1} correspond to C–H, $-\text{C}=\text{O}$, C–O–C stretching vibrations, respectively. All these peaks were also present in the DHT-treated sample, and no new peaks or shifts were observed. The physical treatment DHT under vacuum conditions and at high temperature is known to introduce intermolecular cross-linking by a condensation reaction (i.e., amidation and esterification) by removing the water molecules from the sample.^{22,23} In our case, it was anticipated that the given high temperature ($120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and longer reaction time (24 h) would result in the formation of ester bonds due to condensation reaction between the carboxyl and hydroxyl groups of NFC and CMC in NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h scaffold. However, no peak for ester bond is detected with ATR-IR. Therefore, we further analyzed these samples using solid-state NMR, which also showed the regular cellulosic features of CMC and NFC for both NC3-F and “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” and no new or major shifts of peaks (Figure S6 and Table S1). These results indicate that major changes of the cross-linking/molecular structure (as indirectly confirmed by mechanical strength analysis, see below) occurred only at the interface between NFC and CMC (change in bulk properties would have been otherwise detected by IR or NMR measurements).

XRD was performed to investigate the effect of temperature on the crystalline structure of NC3-F scaffolds before and after DHT. The XRD patterns of NFC, CMC, and the scaffolds before and after DHT are shown in Figure 5B. In agreement with other published works,^{42–44} NFC possesses a typical pattern of crystalline I crystallographic planes as confirmed by the presence of four main diffraction peaks at 2θ values of $14.5^\circ, 16.4^\circ, 20.1^\circ,$ and 34.2° , corresponding to the diffraction

planes of (110), (110), (200), (020), and (004), respectively. For CMC, a broad diffraction pattern was observed at 2θ of 20° , which is attributed to the more amorphous nature of CMC.^{45,46} Interestingly, while the typical diffraction peaks of NFC can be found, the main peak ($2\theta = 20^\circ$) of CMC is covered by the diffraction peak of NFC in NC3-F. All the observed peaks in NC3-F are also present in “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” and no new peaks were visible, showing that the structural properties of the bulk phase of both polymers are preserved after DHT. Thermogravimetric properties of polymers and scaffolds between 40 and $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ before and after DHT are shown in Figure 5C. The curves show that a peak in dTG (the change in mass loss rate) occurred for both scaffold samples at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (NFC, $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; CMC, $92 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) which can be associated with the desorption of physically bound water. After reaching a temperature of $390 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the mass loss for NFC is 74%. In contrast, CMC loses 46% of its mass at $390 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which can be attributed also to the decarboxylation and decomposition of CMC.^{47,48} Both samples of NC3-F and “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” showed a mass loss of 56% at $390 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is 20% less compared to NFC, demonstrating the thermal stability of the scaffolds. dTG (Figure 5D) shows a second peak at $345 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for NFC and at $274 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for CMC. For the scaffold of NC3-F, a new peak was observed at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This peak is also visible at the same position for “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” demonstrating that DHT does surprisingly not change the thermal behavior of the scaffolds despite large differences in the mechanical properties as described below.

3.4. Swelling and *in Vitro* Degradation Studies. Since the scaffolds will be in direct contact with body fluids or cell growth media, their swelling and degradation were analyzed. Especially, swelling may influence the response of cells to the scaffolds and influence cell infiltration, adhesion, growth, and differentiation. Figure 6A shows the swelling kinetics of the NC3-F scaffolds heated to different temperatures (60–120 °C) for 24 h. The as-printed scaffold from the NC3 ink (in wet state prior to freeze-drying) dissolved completely within 2 h in

biofluid, while the NC3-F took 10 h to be disintegrated into several small species in the same medium (Figure S8). As can be seen in Figure 6A, all thermally cross-linked scaffolds showed less swelling and increased stability. An increased absorption of the biofluid up to 12 h followed by an immediate steady state was observed for all cross-linked samples. The scaffold “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” swelled almost 24-fold of its original mass within 12 h. Despite their considerable increase in mass, the sample “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” kept their structural integrity during 24 h in the biofluid (Figure 6C). The swelling capacity of the scaffolds decreased with increasing DHT temperature: NC3-F, 1756 ± 60 (g/g) > “NC3-F-DHT/60 °C/24 h”, 1726 ± 55 (g/g) > “NC3-F-DHT/90 °C/24 h”, 1537 ± 23 (g/g) > “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h”, 1218 ± 44 (g/g). In Figure 6B, the swelling capacities of NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/6–24 h scaffolds swollen in biofluid for 24 h are compared. Although all the scaffolds had slightly different swelling capacity, the most significant difference was found for the scaffold heated for 24 h, which showed a 30% less swelling than the nonheated NC3-F one. This is reasoned by the fact that the longer heating time and higher temperature cause “stronger” physical cross-linking, which substantially limited the swelling capacity of the scaffolds. Such a behavior is well-known for thermally cross-linked cellulose-based materials.³⁷

Results of the *in vitro* degradation studies of NC3-F and cross-linked scaffolds at different temperatures in the presence of biofluid at 37 °C are depicted in Figure 7. NC3-F scaffold

Figure 7. Weight loss of NC3-F scaffold (heated at different temperatures) in cell culture medium at 37 °C. Insert: Images of “NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h” scaffold after being immersed in cell culture medium at 37 °C for the weight loss test. Curves of NC3-F and “NC3-F-DHT/60 °C/24h” end after x and x days due to full disintegration of the material.

disintegrated in 9 h similar to those cross-linked at 60 °C. On the contrary, the disintegration of the scaffold cross-linked at 90 and 120 °C took place mostly in the first 7 days and then slowed down, illustrating that the cross-linking of the polymer chains by DHT prevented rapid degradation. Among these two scaffolds, the one heated at 120 °C was more stable at such conditions, and the mass is reduced only by 60% after 14 days. Stronger cross-linking through DHT and increased interactions between NFC and CMC made the scaffold more resistant in biofluid. The images shown as an insert in Figure 7 suggest that the scaffold was dissolved from the surface to the bulk, and the biofluid treatment is mostly pronounced on the surface of the scaffold. This is allowing one to retain the structural integrity of the scaffold up to 7 days and partial

structural collapse only after 21 and 28 days. The higher temperature in the DHT increased the cross-linking efficiency and thus dimensional stability of the scaffolds. Such increased stability in liquid is usually achieved for scaffolds which are cross-linked by chemical conjugation including carbodiimide, genipin, citric acid, etc.⁴⁹ Through our approach, however, we showed that controlling the intensity of the DHT allows tuning of the scaffold stability in biofluid, which makes our material versatile and also useful for studies on prolonged cell culturing and tissue formation.

3.5. Mechanical Properties. The surface mechanical properties (surface hardness and indentation modulus) of the scaffolds before and after cross-linking were measured in the wet and dry states (see Figure 8). The study on the dry

Figure 8. Mechanical properties obtained through nanoindentation of initial and cross-linked scaffolds before and after immersion in biofluid (BF).

samples revealed clear differences in the local mechanical properties of the scaffolds before and after DHT. DHT increased the surface hardness and the indentation modulus of NC3-F scaffolds from 0.02 to 0.5 MPa and from 1.2 ± 0.2 to 24 ± 3 MPa, respectively. Overall, the local mechanical properties of scaffolds were increased 25-times through this thermal treatment. In wet conditions (scaffolds immersed in biofluid), the mechanical properties of both scaffolds were reduced in comparison to the dry ones. The largest reduction in indentation modulus had the scaffold NC3-F (80% reduction with respect to dry state). The DHT-treated (cross-linked) samples were more wet-resilient; the indentation modulus decreased only by 20% when immersed in biofluid and the hardness from 0.5 ± 0.1 MPa to 0.25 ± 0.1 MPa. To the best of our knowledge, no reports on determining the local properties of cellulose-based scaffolds are available in the literature. Therefore, we correlated our values to those of soft tissues. For example, the indentation modulus determined for DHT samples are comparable to the value reported by Dias et al. for central cornea.⁵⁰ In general, the reduction of mechanical properties in a wet state is a result of the swelling of the samples and resulting water plasticization effect. Cross-linking by DHT increased considerably the wet resilience of the samples.

The mechanical properties of the scaffolds in the wet state immersed in biofluid were further analyzed by unconfined compression testing.⁵¹ Figure 9A,C compare the mechanical properties of scaffolds cross-linked at different temperatures ranging from 60 to 120 °C for a fixed heating time of 24 h.

Figure 9. Stress–strain curves and comparative mechanical properties scaffolds thermally treated at different temperatures (A,C) and at different times at 120 °C (B,D). Compressive stress was determined at 30% compression, and the compressive stiffness equals the tangent modulus at 30% strain.

Figure 10. (A) Human osteoblast cell’s viability on the inks and scaffolds using an MTT assay. (B,C) Fluorescence images of a live/dead assay of osteoblast cells cultured on NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h scaffold (B, surface and C, interior/cross-section). Statistical significance was defined as $P < 0.05$ compared to the control sample (ANOVA test). Samples that show a significant difference compared to the control sample are marked with an asterisk *.

Even though there are minor improvement of the mechanical properties of the scaffolds cross-linked at 60 and 90 °C, the obtained values (compressive stress at 30% strain and elastic modulus) are not statistically different (P -values < 0.05) to

those of non-cross-linked NC3-F scaffold. In contrast to this, DHT at 120 °C for 6–24 h significantly increased the compressive stress (Figure 9B,D). When subjected to compression and subsequent relaxation, all samples showed a

considerable quasi-plastic deformation (Figure S9), indicative for a large energy dissipation in the scaffolds. Such a tendency was also noticed for natural cartilage when tested in compression mode.⁵² With increasing DHT time, the compressive stress at 30% strain of the scaffolds was significantly increased from 1.7 kPa (NC3-F) up to 31 kPa (NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/12 h). This represents an increase of almost 20 times. Comparable values were also reported for 3D printed hydrogels from NFC alginate (cross-linked with calcium chloride) featuring a compressive stress of 32 kPa.⁹ Concomitantly with the compressive stress, the Young's moduli increased by prolonging the heating time of DHT at 120 °C: from 37 kPa for "NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/6 h" to 79 kPa for "NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/12 h". Increasing heating time from 12 to 24 h did not further increase the mechanical properties. Similar observations were also made in the case of the compressive stiffness (tangent modulus at 30% strain), and it increased with heating time to a maximum value of 206 ± 54 kPa (NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/12 h), which is 121-fold higher than the respective modulus of NC3-F. We believe that the significantly increased mechanical properties after the DHT are related to strong physical cross-linking of CMC with the NCF surface (as was already discussed in previous sections). It is important to notice that these improved mechanical properties were achieved without involving any additional cross-linkers while preserving the printed three-dimensional shape (no shrinkage was observed). Comparing these results with reported data, the mechanical properties of the produced NCF/CMC scaffolds are suitable for both cartilage and bone tissue engineering (TE).⁵³

3.6. Biocompatibility Test. Figure 10 shows the influence of the inks and scaffolds (compared to the control cell growth medium) on the cell viability of human osteoblasts. Statistical significance: *p* values of 0.05 or lower are shown with an asterisk. In undiluted and 1:2 diluted form, the ink NC3 caused a significant reduction in cell viability compared to the control. All other materials did either not reduce or surprisingly even increased the cell viability. This is most likely related to the spatially resolved patterns and interconnected pores of this sample, which suits the osteoblasts cells, which in their native environment (i.e., the bone) attach most of the time to "solid substrates". Since the increase in cell viability reaches ~40% for cross-linked samples compared to the control (again regardless of the dilution), these samples can be of interest for further testing in bone tissue engineering applications, maybe even for some bone replacement therapies. The improvements in cell viability for other samples, although lower compared to the cross-linked sample, still could make these materials promising for the same type of applications, albeit maybe more for short-term implantations, in which they could serve as substrates for the promotion of osteoblast growth.

Finally, to get further insight into the cell viability after their exposure to the samples, a so-called "direct-contact" test was performed. For this purpose, the osteoblast cells were seeded on NC3-F-DHT/120 °C/24 h scaffolds (as described in the Experimental Section), followed by dying with the Live/Dead kit, showing viable (green) and dead (red) cells. Figure 10B,C shows the fluorescence images of Live/Dead assay of osteoblast cells after 3 days of incubation on the scaffolds. To visualize the distribution of seeded cells on the entire scaffolds, the surface and cross-section of cut samples (see Figure S10) were considered for fluorescence microscope analysis. Considering the attachment of viable cells (no dead

cells) on both the surface (Figure 10B) and at the interior/cross-section (Figure 10C) of the scaffold after the mentioned exposure period, it could be proposed that the freeze-dried and DHT sample pose no harm to the used osteoblast cells, suggesting that the biocompatible NFC/CMC materials shall be potentially used in bone tissue engineering applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Composite inks from plant based nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC) and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) were prepared and shaped into dual-porous scaffolds by extrusion based three-dimensional printing. We developed a new ink based on commercially available NFC and CMC, i.e., NC3. This ink consisting of 1.5 wt % NFC and 6 wt % CMC featured the highest viscosity and shear moduli combined with the strongest shear-thinning behavior, resulting in the best shape fidelity for the printed structure (in comparison to pure CMC, NFC, and other studied ink formulations). The macroporosity (200–500 μm diameter) of the scaffolds could be controlled by adjusting the printing strand distance and dispensing pressure. Freeze-drying retained the macroscopic shape of the print while creating interconnected micropores (20–90 μm) in each strand. The wet resilience and mechanical properties of the scaffolds were further improved by dehydrothermal treatment (DHT) causing physical cross-linking while preserving the shape of the prints. Performing this treatment at 120 °C increased the surface hardness (0.5 MPa), compressive stress (~60 kPa), and elastic modulus (180 kPa) of the prints. The heat-treated scaffolds showed a long-term (4 weeks) dimensional stability in biofluid. The scaffolds showed excellent biocompatibility and improved proliferation and inflicted no harm to bone tissue derived osteoblast cells. Overall, scaffolds with tunable multiscale porosity, fluid-uptake capacity, degradation, and mechanical properties were prepared. The biocompatible and low-cost inks developed NFC and CMC through a green approach in this work is suitable to mimic both the physiological functions and components of ECM (e.g., glycoproteins). Given the biocompatibility of NFC/CMC ink with lower concentration of cells, they could be potentially used for developing cell-laden materials and for 3D bioprinting. Moreover, the handling and sterilization of dry scaffolds is an easy process. Considering the given versatility of both inks and scaffolds, the proposed generic approach appears to be suitable for the design of stable biobased templates for the growth and development of various biological tissues (e.g., cartilage or bones). Our system can be made even more versatile by introducing cell-adhesion sites (e.g., amino acids, peptides, proteins) and cross-linkers (e.g., thiol–ene chemistry), a work currently under progress. Though the developed scaffold materials were not tested for *in vivo* applications, which might be one of the limitation of this study, the work related to the fabrication of cell-laden biomaterials for *in vivo* experiments are currently under progress, which will be published elsewhere.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsabm.9b01099>.

Results of ink flow, shape fidelity, frequency dependent storage modulus, loss tangent of inks, and solid-state NMR of inks, charge titration and stress–strain curves of

the scaffolds, and photo image of the scaffolds seeded with osteoblast cells (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Tamilselvan Mohan – Laboratory for Characterisation and Processing of Polymers, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maribor, 2000 Maribor, Slovenia; orcid.org/0000-0002-8569-1642; Phone: +386 2220 7746; Email: tamilselvan.mohan@um.si

Karin Stana Kleinschek – Institute of Chemistry and Technology of Biobased System, Graz University of Technology, 8010 Graz, Austria; Institute of Automation, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Maribor, 2000 Maribor, Slovenia; Phone: +4331687632070; Email: karin.stanakleinschek@tugraz.at

Authors

Andreja Dobaj Štiglic – Laboratory for Characterisation and Processing of Polymers, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maribor, 2000 Maribor, Slovenia

Marco Beaumont – Institute of Chemistry of Renewable Resources, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), 3430 Tulln, Austria; orcid.org/0000-0002-2571-497X

Johannes Konnerth – Department of Material Sciences and Process Engineering, Institute of Wood Technology and Renewable Materials, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), 3430 Tulln, Austria

Fazilet Güner – Laboratory for Characterisation and Processing of Polymers, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maribor, 2000 Maribor, Slovenia

Damjan Makuc – National Institute of Chemistry, SI-1001 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Uroš Maver – Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, University of Maribor, SI-2000 Maribor, Slovenia; orcid.org/0000-0002-2237-3786

Lidija Gradišnik – Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Biomedical Sciences, University of Maribor, SI-2000 Maribor, Slovenia

Janez Plavec – National Institute of Chemistry, SI-1001 Ljubljana, Slovenia; orcid.org/0000-0003-1570-8602

Rupert Kargl – Laboratory for Characterisation and Processing of Polymers, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Institute of Automation, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Maribor, 2000 Maribor, Slovenia; Institute of Paper, Pulp and Fibre Technology (IPZ), Graz University of Technology, A-8010 Graz, Austria; orcid.org/0000-0003-4327-7053

Complete contact information is available at: <https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acsabm.9b01099>

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support for this study received from the Slovenian Research Agency (Grant Nos. P2-0118, P3-0036, J4-1764, and I0-0029). Prof. Gindl-Altmatter is

acknowledged for providing access to the rheometer. The authors would like to acknowledge the Smart Lab (a core facility supported by the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research and Anton Paar GmbH/Austria, and Dr. Angela Chemelli from the Graz University of Technology/Austria).

REFERENCES

- (1) Mohan, T.; Maver, T.; Štiglic, A. D.; Stana-Kleinschek, K.; Kargl, R. 3D bioprinting of polysaccharides and their derivatives: From characterization to application. In *Fundamental Biomaterials: Polymers*; Woodhead Publishing, 2018; pp 105–141.
- (2) Loh, Q. L.; Choong, C. Three-dimensional scaffolds for tissue engineering applications: role of porosity and pore size. *Tissue Eng., Part B* **2013**, *19*, 485–502.
- (3) Sampath, U. G. T. M.; Ching, Y. C.; Chuah, C. H.; Sabariah, J. J.; Lin, P.-C. Fabrication of Porous Materials from Natural/Synthetic Biopolymers and Their Composites. *Materials* **2016**, *9*, 991.
- (4) Derakhshanfar, S.; Mbeleck, R.; Xu, K.; Zhang, X.; Zhong, W.; Xing, M. 3D bioprinting for biomedical devices and tissue engineering: A review of recent trends and advances. *Bioact Mater.* **2018**, *3*, 144–156.
- (5) Moreno Madrid, A. P.; Vrech, S. M.; Sanchez, M. A.; Rodriguez, A. P. Advances in additive manufacturing for bone tissue engineering scaffolds. *Mater. Sci. Eng., C* **2019**, *100*, 631–644.
- (6) Cidonio, G.; Glinka, M.; Dawson, J. I.; Oreffo, R. O. C. The cell in the ink: Improving biofabrication by printing stem cells for skeletal regenerative medicine. *Biomaterials* **2019**, *209*, 10–24.
- (7) Wang, X.; Lou, T.; Zhao, W.; Song, G.; Li, C.; Cui, G. The effect of fiber size and pore size on cell proliferation and infiltration in PLLA scaffolds on bone tissue engineering. *J. Biomater. Appl.* **2016**, *30*, 1545–1551.
- (8) Bohner, M.; Loosli, Y.; Baroud, G.; Lacroix, D. Commentary: Deciphering the link between architecture and biological response of a bone graft substitute. *Acta Biomater.* **2011**, *7*, 478–484.
- (9) Markstedt, K.; Mantas, A.; Tournier, I.; Martínez Ávila, H.; Hägg, D.; Gatenholm, P. 3D Bioprinting Human Chondrocytes with Nanocellulose–Alginate Bioink for Cartilage Tissue Engineering Applications. *Biomacromolecules* **2015**, *16*, 1489–1496.
- (10) Huan, S.; Ajdary, R.; Bai, L.; Klar, V.; Rojas, O. J. Low Solids Emulsion Gels Based on Nanocellulose for 3D-Printing. *Biomacromolecules* **2019**, *20*, 635–644.
- (11) Tchobanian, A.; Van Oosterwyck, H.; Fardim, P. Polysaccharides for tissue engineering: Current landscape and future prospects. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2019**, *205*, 601–625.
- (12) Prakash Menon, M.; Selvakumar, R.; Suresh kumar, P.; Ramakrishna, S. Extraction and modification of cellulose nanofibers derived from biomass for environmental application. *RSC Adv.* **2017**, *7*, 42750–42773.
- (13) Apelgren, P.; Karabulut, E.; Amoroso, M.; Mantas, A.; Martínez Ávila, H.; Kölby, L.; Kondo, T.; Toriz, G.; Gatenholm, P. In Vivo Human Cartilage Formation in Three-Dimensional Bioprinted Constructs with a Novel Bacterial Nanocellulose Bioink. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **2019**, *5*, 2482–2490.
- (14) Mohan, T.; Hribernik, S.; Kargl, R.; Kleinschek, K. S., Nanocellulosic Materials in Tissue Engineering Applications. In *Cellulose - Fundamental Aspects and Current Trends*; Intech Open, 2015.
- (15) Nguyen, D.; Hägg, D. A.; Forsman, A.; Ekholm, J.; Nimkingratana, P.; Brantsing, C.; Kalogeropoulos, T.; Zaunz, S.; Concaro, S.; Brittberg, M.; Lindahl, A.; Gatenholm, P.; Enejder, A.; Simonsson, S. Cartilage Tissue Engineering by the 3D Bioprinting of iPS Cells in a Nanocellulose/Alginate Bioink. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 658.
- (16) Orelma, H.; Johansson, L.-s.; Filpponen, I.; Rojas, O. J.; Laine, J. Generic Method for Attaching Biomolecules via Avidin–Biotin Complexes Immobilized on Films of Regenerated and Nanofibrillar Cellulose. *Biomacromolecules* **2012**, *13*, 2802–2810.

- (17) Wong, T. W.; Ramli, N. A. Carboxymethylcellulose film for bacterial wound infection control and healing. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2014**, *112*, 367–375.
- (18) Maver, T.; Smrke, D. M.; Kurečić, M.; Gradišnik, L.; Maver, U.; Kleinschek, K. S. Combining 3D printing and electrospinning for preparation of pain-relieving wound-dressing materials. *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *88*, 33–48.
- (19) Maver, T.; Kurečić, M.; Smrke, D. M.; Kleinschek, K. S.; Maver, U. Electrospun nanofibrous CMC/PEO as a part of an effective pain-relieving wound dressing. *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* **2016**, *79*, 475–486.
- (20) Petta, D.; Armiento, A. R.; Grijpma, D.; Alini, M.; Eglin, D.; D'Este, M. 3D bioprinting of a hyaluronan bioink through enzymatic- and visible light-crosslinking. *Biofabrication* **2018**, *10*, No. 044104.
- (21) Jung, C. S.; Kim, B. K.; Lee, J.; Min, B.-H.; Park, S.-H. Development of Printable Natural Cartilage Matrix Bioink for 3D Printing of Irregular Tissue Shape. *Tissue Eng. Regen. Med.* **2018**, *15*, 155–162.
- (22) Drexler, J. W.; Powell, H. M. Dehydrothermal Crosslinking of Electrospun Collagen. *Tissue Eng., Part C* **2011**, *17*, 9–17.
- (23) Haugh, M. G.; Jaasma, M. J.; O'Brien, F. J. The effect of dehydrothermal treatment on the mechanical and structural properties of collagen-GAG scaffolds. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part A* **2009**, *89A*, 363–369.
- (24) Nečas, D.; Klapetek, P. Gwyddion: an open-source software for SPM data analysis. *Cent. Eur. J. Phys.* **2012**, *10*, 181–188.
- (25) Zemljic, L. F.; Cakara, D.; Michaelis, N.; Heinze, T.; Stana Kleinschek, K. Protonation behavior of 6-deoxy-6-(2-aminoethyl)-amino cellulose: a potentiometric titration study. *Cellulose* **2011**, *18*, 33–43.
- (26) Rueden, C. T.; Schindelin, J.; Hiner, M. C.; DeZonia, B. E.; Walter, A. E.; Arena, E. T.; Eliceiri, K. W. ImageJ2: ImageJ for the next generation of scientific image data. *BMC Bioinf.* **2017**, *18*, 529.
- (27) Zhang, Y.; Ye, L.; Cui, J.; Yang, B.; Sun, H.; Li, J.; Yao, F. A biomimetic poly (vinyl alcohol)–carrageenan composite scaffold with oriented microarchitecture. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **2016**, *2*, 544–557.
- (28) Finšgar, M.; Uzunalić, A. P.; Stergar, J.; Gradišnik, L.; Maver, U. Novel chitosan/diclofenac coatings on medical grade stainless steel for hip replacement applications. *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 26653.
- (29) Maver, U.; Xhanari, K.; Zizek, M.; Korte, D.; Gradišnik, L.; Franko, M.; Finšgar, M. A combination of interdisciplinary analytical tools for evaluation of multi-layered coatings on medical grade stainless steel for biomedical applications. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* **2018**, *128*, 230–246.
- (30) Stergar, J.; Ban, I.; Gradišnik, L.; Maver, U. Novel drug delivery system based on NiCu nanoparticles for targeting various cells. *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *88*, 57–65.
- (31) Sigma-Aldrich. 04511 Cellstain double staining kit, <https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/catalog/product/sigma/04511?lang=en®ion=SI> (accessed March 2, 2018).
- (32) Murphy, C. M.; Haugh, M. G.; O'Brien, F. J. The effect of mean pore size on cell attachment, proliferation and migration in collagen–glycosaminoglycan scaffolds for bone tissue engineering. *Biomaterials* **2010**, *31*, 461–466.
- (33) Karageorgiou, V.; Kaplan, D. Porosity of 3D biomaterial scaffolds and osteogenesis. *Biomaterials* **2005**, *26*, 5474–5491.
- (34) Harnkarnsujarit, N.; Kawai, K.; Watanabe, M.; Suzuki, T. Effects of freezing on microstructure and rehydration properties of freeze-dried soybean curd. *J. Food Eng.* **2016**, *184*, 10–20.
- (35) Yano, S.; Hatakeyama, H.; Hatakeyama, T. Effect of hydrogen bond formation on dynamic mechanical properties of amorphous cellulose. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **1976**, *20*, 3221–3231.
- (36) Kato, K. L.; Cameron, R. E. Structure–property relationships in thermally aged cellulose fibers and paper. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **1999**, *74*, 1465–1477.
- (37) Mohan, T.; Spirk, S.; Kargl, R.; Doliška, A.; Vesel, A.; Salzmann, I.; Resel, R.; Ribitsch, V.; Stana-Kleinschek, K. Exploring the rearrangement of amorphous cellulose model thin films upon heat treatment. *Soft Matter* **2012**, *8*, 9807–9815.
- (38) Wessels, Q. B.; Pretorius, E. Enhanced stabilization of collagen-based dermal regeneration scaffolds through the combination of physical and chemical crosslinking. *S. Afr. J. Sci.* **2008**, *104*, 513–516.
- (39) Bružauskaitė, I.; Bironaitė, D.; Bagdonas, E.; Bernotienė, E. Scaffolds and cells for tissue regeneration: different scaffold pore sizes—different cell effects. *Cytotechnology* **2016**, *68*, 355–369.
- (40) Tienen, T. G.; Heijkants, R. G. J. C.; de Groot, J. H.; Pennings, A. J.; Schouten, A. J.; Veth, R. P. H.; Buma, P. Replacement of the Knee Meniscus by a Porous Polymer Implant: A Study in Dogs. *Am. J. Sports Med.* **2006**, *34*, 64–71.
- (41) Matsiko, A.; Gleeson, J. P.; O'Brien, F. J. Scaffold Mean Pore Size Influences Mesenchymal Stem Cell Chondrogenic Differentiation and Matrix Deposition. *Tissue Eng., Part A* **2015**, *21*, 486–497.
- (42) Khalil, A. M.; Hassan, M. L.; Ward, A. A. Novel nanofibrillated cellulose/polyvinylpyrrolidone/silver nanoparticles films with electrical conductivity properties. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2017**, *157*, 503–511.
- (43) Miao, J.; Yu, Y.; Jiang, Z.; Zhang, L. One-pot preparation of hydrophobic cellulose nanocrystals in an ionic liquid. *Cellulose* **2016**, *23*, 1209–1219.
- (44) French, A. D. Idealized powder diffraction patterns for cellulose polymorphs. *Cellulose* **2014**, *21*, 885–896.
- (45) Ahmad, M.; Manzoor, K.; Ahmad, S.; Ikram, S. Preparation, Kinetics, Thermodynamics, and Mechanism Evaluation of Thiosemicarbazide Modified Green Carboxymethyl Cellulose as an Efficient Cu(II) Adsorbent. *J. Chem. Eng. Data* **2018**, *63*, 1905–1916.
- (46) Zhao, Q.; Qian, J.; An, Q.; Gui, Z.; Jin, H.; Yin, M. Pervaporation dehydration of isopropanol using homogeneous polyelectrolyte complex membranes of poly-(diallyldimethylammonium chloride)/sodium carboxymethyl cellulose. *J. Membr. Sci.* **2009**, *329*, 175–182.
- (47) Xing, R.; Wang, X.; Zhang, C.; Wang, J.; Zhang, Y.; Song, Y.; Guo, Z. Superparamagnetic magnetite nanocrystal clusters as potential magnetic carriers for the delivery of platinum anticancer drugs. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2011**, *21*, 11142–11149.
- (48) Ibrahim, A. A.; Adel, A. M.; El-Wahab, Z. H. A.; Al-Shemy, M. T. Utilization of carboxymethyl cellulose based on bean hulls as chelating agent. Synthesis, characterization and biological activity. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2011**, *83*, 94–115.
- (49) Oryan, A.; Kamali, A.; Moshiri, A.; Baharvand, H.; Daemi, H. Chemical crosslinking of biopolymeric scaffolds: Current knowledge and future directions of crosslinked engineered bone scaffolds. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2018**, *107*, 678–688.
- (50) Dias, J. M.; Ziebarth, N. M. Anterior and posterior corneal stroma elasticity assessed using nanoindentation. *Exp. Eye Res.* **2013**, *115*, 41–46.
- (51) Sarem, M.; Moztarzadeh, F.; Mozafari, M. How can genipin assist gelatin/carbohydrate chitosan scaffolds to act as replacements of load-bearing soft tissues? *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2013**, *93*, 635–643.
- (52) Kerin, A. J.; Wisnom, M. R.; Adams, M. A. The compressive strength of articular cartilage. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Part H* **1998**, *212*, 273–280.
- (53) Wescoe, K. E.; Schugar, R. C.; Chu, C. R.; Deasy, B. M. The Role of the Biochemical and Biophysical Environment in Chondrogenic Stem Cell Differentiation Assays and Cartilage Tissue Engineering. *Cell Biochem. Biophys.* **2008**, *52*, 85–102.